

UNDERPIN

DATA SPACE FOR MANUFACTURING

Pan-European data space for holistic asset management in critical manufacturing industries

D6.1 Integrated Communication and Dissemination Plan (initial design)

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CDB	Communication and Dissemination Board
DS	Data Space
EAB	External Advisory Board
EBDVF	European Big Data Value Forum
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
PM	Project Manager
PR	Press release
SEB	Sustainability and Ecosystem Board
SME	Small and Midsize Enterprise
SWC	Semantic Web Company
TP	Tiko Pro
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package
WS	Workshop
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium

Executive summary

The UNDERPIN project aims to establish the Pan-European Data Space for holistic asset management in critical manufacturing industries, in the fields of dynamic asset management and predictive/ prescriptive maintenance that will ensure cross-organizational and cross-use-case data sharing and exchange.

Specifically tailored for European manufacturers in the refinery and renewable energy domains, the UNDERPIN platform is poised to revolutionize how industries approach data-driven solutions. With a strong focus on fostering collaboration between SMEs and large industry players, the UNDERPIN Data Spaces aims to drive innovation, enhance products and services, and elevate the industry to new heights of efficiency.

The document sets out a comprehensive framework for all dissemination activities, offering a set of guidelines to be adhered to by all partners. It specifies the methods and tools to be utilized for the project communication needs. As a living document, it can be revised to incorporate new opportunities that emerge throughout the project lifespan.

The communication strategy prioritizes increasing awareness of the project, involving key stakeholders, sharing the project findings, laying the groundwork for utilizing the project outcomes, and coordinating efforts with other pertinent initiatives and projects.

1 Introduction

The subsequent segment outlines the fundamental structure of the communication plan and presents an overview of the intended approach for planned communication initiatives for the UNDERPIN project.

1.1 Purpose of the document

This deliverable has been written as part of *Work Package 6 – Communication, Dissemination & Scale Out*. The purpose of deliverable *D6.1 – Integrated Communication and Dissemination Plan (initial design)* is to coordinate all communication and dissemination activities within the project, offering guidelines for all partners to follow.

With the goal of maximizing impact for the entire project in a cohesive manner, specific objectives include:

- achieving consensus on a unified communication plan that all partners will adhere to, ensuring consistency and efficiency in all dissemination activities
- preparing and regularly updating a plan for disseminating results, which includes documenting completed dissemination activities and outlining those still in the planning stages
- specifying Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and establishing a dissemination and communication metrics system for ongoing collection and analysis. This system will monitor various metrics and KPIs, such as website visitors, social media followers, published articles, organized workshops, and participation in events, ensuring continuous evaluation and improvement of the project's outreach and impact
- defining communication channels and tools that will raise awareness and project visibility. This includes website development, managing social media channels, preparation of flyers, banners, PR, etc
- laying out the rules for a website, social media accounts and communication materials, organisation of events (following the provisions of the GREEN CHARTER on the sustainable implementation of project activities and event organisation), relations with media, billboards, plaques, or any other printed or electronic displays that will be used
- reaching the specified target community of the European manufacturing industry – with a strong focus on creating added value and impact for SMEs - as well as informing the society to promote the project activities and results and thereby maximising the impact

This comprehensive document outlines the methodology, tools for communication, and a specific timeline. As a dynamic working document, it can be amended to seize opportunities as they arise throughout the project duration.

The WP6 Lead, Tiko Pro, will regularly update the PM on progress through status reports at three-month intervals. Additionally, bi-annual progress reports, along with recommendations, will be prepared for presentation at GA meetings.

1.2 Relation to other project work

This deliverable will be used to provide input to the following deliverables:

- *D5.3 Business, engagement, and commercialisation plan:* it will define the methods to reaching out to a large variety of stakeholders (European manufacturers: data providers, data consumers), data ecosystems and public initiatives (related EU projects, competence centers, professional associations, and technology platforms) to ensure the development of a sustainable Data Space. Also, it will deliver a comprehensive business and sustainability concept-focused (as opposed to technology) assessment of the most immediate and realistic market opportunities for UNDERPIN. Defining the strategy for bringing the UNDERPIN to market. It will also develop a clear pricing model along the specified business model. This deliverable will describe a market watchdog mechanism to identify potential competitors for UNDERPIN upon entering the market while following the communication rules stated in D6.1.

- *D5.2 Trust creation processes design:* This deliverable will provide a comprehensive analysis of the legal and ethical framework and challenges relevant to the UNDERPIN Data Space, which involves the identification of relevant legislation, principles, and values regarding the sharing of personal and non-personal, including industrial, data within the context of the targeted sectors. It will provide a roadmap for the definition of a viable, feasible, and sustainable business model for the UNDERPIN Data Space.

D6.2 Final Communication, Exploitation, Dissemination, and Pre-standardisation Plan and Activities report. In particular, D6.2 will report on the activities as proposed in D6.1 and will evaluate their effectiveness against specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), concurrently used for assessing the overall UNDERPIN impact achieved.

1.3 Milestones and deliverables of WP6

The existing marketing tools and channels will be utilized to communicate achieved milestones. All deliverables classified with a dissemination level of "PU - Public" will be uploaded to the project website.

No	Milestone Name	Description	Due Month
MS12	CDP definition and production of communication material	The document will provide further elaborated CDP structure, as it was initially drafted at the stage of proposal preparation, containing activities to be performed, including rules and guidelines for provision of these actions to maximize the impact of UNDERPIN.	M6

MS13	CDP action completed	All CDP activities, initiated at the start of the project and updated mid-way and at the project end, have been successfully implemented to achieve the impacts as stipulated in the CDP.	M24
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Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Lead BEN	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Month
D6.1	Integrated Communication, Exploitation and Dissemination Plan (initial design)	TP	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M6
D6.2	Final Communication, Exploitation, Dissemination and Pre-standardisation Plan and Activities report	TP	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M24

As per the process outlined in D1.1, the following internal deadlines apply:

Actions	Deliverable D6.1	Deliverable D6.2
ToC ready	29.2.2024	31.8.2025
80% ready	30.3.2024	30.9.2025
Final draft per peer review	30.4.2024	31.10.2025
Submission	30.5.2024	30.11.2025
Peer review	ARC, SWC	ARC, INNOV

2 Dissemination and communication plan

This chapter outlines the essential framework of the communication and dissemination plan for the UNDERPIN project. It details the roles and responsibilities of each partner in implementing the plan, the reporting process, and the guidelines for using key messages and the EU emblem in communications.

Additionally, the chapter defines the objectives of the Communication and Dissemination (CD) Plan, identifies the target audience, and specifies the key messages that will be conveyed through various media channels and CD tools. It also describes the strategies for communication, dissemination, exploitation, and business growth, as well as the methodologies employed to meet the project communication needs effectively. Furthermore, this chapter includes specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for measuring both dissemination-related activities and communication-related activities, ensuring that all efforts are effectively tracked and evaluated.

2.1 Communication and dissemination board

All partners will actively work to disseminate the project results at the local/regional/national and EU level. All partners will use various tools and resources to disseminate project outputs and activities, and thus allow their valorisation both at the national and European level.

Every beneficiary will appoint one representative in the Communication and Dissemination Board (CDB) who will advocate for the project outreach and community building. As a lead beneficiary of WP 6: Communication and Dissemination, TIKO PRO (TP) will chair the CDB.

The chair of CDB implies maintaining close ties with the chair of the Sustainability and Ecosystem Board (SEB), appointed by the lead beneficiary MOH, as well as the External Advisory Board (EAB), as only through the close-knit partnership of all appointed UNDERPIN governance bodies, we will succeed in boosting awareness of the future common European data spaces and in creating new opportunities through digitalisation. One of the major objectives of these operations will thus be to establish sustainable links with the target community and to facilitate effective communication and dissemination with other data space initiatives and schemes.

On the consortium level, CDB will be in charge of the delivery and monitoring of communication and dissemination of project results to relevant stakeholders, i.e. professional and lay audience as well as for suggesting updates to the CDP to ensure visibility, proper external information flow, and project PR. The chair of CDB will report to the PM on the progress via status reports at regular intervals every 3 (three) months and will prepare bi-annual progress reports with recommendations for GA meetings.

Members of the CDB board are as follows:

Name	Beneficiary
Konstantinos Chatzifotis	MOH
Stelios Sartzetakis	ARC
Martin Kaltenböck	SWC
George Chrysokentis	WM
Axel Weißenfeld	AIT

Odysseas Kokkinos	INNOV-ACTS
Victoria Katsarou	SPH
Sofia Visvardi	MORE
Sandra Bortek	TP

2.2 Objectives of the dissemination activities and plan

The primary aim of dissemination is to educate key target audiences about the goals, progress, outcomes, and outputs of the UNDERPIN project and the UNDERPIN Data Space. This, in turn, ensures that the project results and deliverables are accessible to both the intended target groups and a broader audience. Dissemination increases also visibility of the project and ensures sustainability beyond the project end.

The main objective of the Communication and Dissemination plan is to populate the UNDERPIN Data Space and thereby scale out UNDERPIN to a successful European Data Space for Manufacturing.

The key dissemination objectives are:

- keeping the stakeholders and partners informed on progress made and milestones reached
- sharing the project activities, outputs, results, and added value to target groups
- promoting UNDERPIN Data Space and creating impact
- raising awareness among target groups through highlighting the benefits of joining (SMEs focused)
- SMEs engagement – getting the early adopters and onboarding SMEs
- community building - building synergies with other data spaces, projects, networks, initiatives (orchestration and scale-out)
- promoting awareness of sustainability, circularity, and green issues arising from our project and of relevant EU-wide initiatives and expert groups.

These objectives follow the overall goal of the project - to build and establish a populated UNDERPIN Data Space for Manufacturing in Europe with an established community of Data Space participants.

The plan will undergo regular updates and reviews by project partners as the project unfolds, allowing for adjustments as work progresses and new opportunities for dissemination become apparent and recognized.

2.3 Target groups and key messages

Communication and dissemination activities will be adapted and tailored to reach the specified target community of the European manufacturing industry - with a strong focus on creating added value and impact for SMEs.

Three main stakeholder categories have been defined. Each stakeholder group has its own purpose for the UNDERPIN project and all are equally important.

Table 1 Stakeholder Target Groups

	Categories	Main messages	Description	Explanation
A	EU REFERENCE PROJECTS	Synergies, best practices, experience exchange.	Any project, initiative, activities, data space that we can learn from.	We can learn from any project, initiative, activity, or data space by understanding their processes, challenges, and successes. It could mean conducting thorough research, participating in relevant events and workshops, networking with professionals in the field, and studying available resources such as reports, case studies, and documentation. By analysing different approaches, methodologies, and outcomes, we can identify best practices, innovative solutions, and valuable insights that can inform our own project development and implementation. Additionally, seeking feedback and lessons learned from others can help us avoid common pitfalls and optimize our strategies for success.
B	MULTIPLIERS	Connectors, spread the news, get the message across, entry point for data space members.	Associations, Hubs or similar that can connect us with reference projects, stakeholders.	1. STEP: exploring partnerships with organizations like associations or hubs to facilitate connections with reference projects or stakeholders. 2. STEP: use them as a channel to communicate UNDERPIN project, partner in a way to help us reach broader audience (primary stakeholders-SMEs), a cooperate in organising project events in the second year of the project.
C	DATA SPACE ONBOARDING (STAKEHOLDERS)	Data space benefits/advantages, why to join?	Stakeholders that we want to attract to the data space (SMEs, Large companies, research organisations, maybe NGO that see the benefits of the data.	SMEs as well as other organisations can benefit from access to resources and expertise they may not have internally, while large companies can leverage the innovation and agility of SMEs to drive their own initiatives forward. Research organizations bring valuable knowledge and capabilities to the table, contributing to the development of cutting-edge solutions. NGOs can provide valuable perspectives on the societal impact and ethical considerations of data usage. Engaging with this diverse set of stakeholders ensures a well-rounded and inclusive approach to building and utilizing the data space.

A stakeholders list will be generated with input from all partners, including contact details of potentially interested organizations, experts, and professionals as well as media (in each country).

Communication activities will also address a broader target audience to explain the benefits of data spaces and to clarify the concept of data spaces itself, as well as to communicate the USP (unique selling proposition) and thereby value of participation in the UNDERPIN Data Space. The goal of this communication is to understand public concerns, reduce resistance to such projects, and provide information for a better understanding of the matter. Informing society to promote the project activities and results will maximise the impact. Such specified end-users are machine users, machine vendors, maintenance service providers, remanufacturers, manufacturers, reuse, repairing, refurbishing, and recycling companies, and beyond. The main objective is to populate the UNDERPIN Data Space and thereby scale out UNDERPIN to a successful European Data Space for Manufacturing.

The communication activities will focus on the following key messages (and others that will be defined as the project evolves), which will be tailored to the target audience:

- European manufacturers in the refinery and renewable energy domains, their value chain ecosystem of SMEs, and governmental, research, and civil society stakeholders will be equipped with sustainable and secure yet user-friendly Data Space, aiming at improving processes, cost structure, and material management via beyond the state-of-the-art data analysis.
- The solution is compliant with EU and international standards, with Data related Acts, IDSA, and GAIA-X guidelines encompassing enterprise-ready infrastructure and tools to accommodate secure and trusted data, improving company operations.
- UNDERPIN Data Space will provide cross-organizational and cross-use-case data sharing and exchanging, a solution that ensures data sovereignty, with a strong focus on the interplay of SMEs and large industry players to improve products and services.
- UNDERPIN Data Space ensures higher performance, better insight into assets critically, reduced overall downtimes and maintenance costs, extended machine usage periods, improved future machine designs, new service models, improved production line operations, company-internal processes, increased usability, and enhanced business opportunities for industrial data value-added services, supporting the transition towards a circular economy.

To define the project, we will utilize taglines that succinctly describe its essence, such as:

- Data Space for European Manufacturing Excellence
- Collaborate, Innovate, Transform - European Data Space Unleashed.

Additionally, the project will incorporate various claims specific to individual campaigns developed throughout its duration. Some of the claims that can and will be used are stated here, others will be developed as the project progresses.

- Revolutionizing Manufacturing Through UNDERPIN: Unleashing the Power of a European Data Space.
- UNDERPIN - Empowering European Industry through Data Space.
- Driving Innovation, Enhancing Efficiency. UNDERPIN - Data Space Solution for EU Manufacturing.
- Transforming Industry Dynamics: UNDERPIN - Secure Data Space for Next-Gen Manufacturing.
- Beyond Boundaries. UNDERPIN - European Data Space for Manufacturing Excellence.
- Collaboration Unleashed. UNDERPIN - Cross-Organizational Data Space for Manufacturing Advancement.
- Unlocking Potential, Unleashing Innovation: UNDERPIN's Data Space for Manufacturing Success.

2.4 Methodology

This chapter provides a detailed look at how UNDERPIN plans to achieve and sustain a high level of engagement and impact throughout the project duration and beyond. It first explores the strategic overview, which details UNDERPIN's approach to integrating innovative practices and frameworks, such as the Quintuple Helix Innovation model. Following this, the methodology section outlines the structured, systematic approach to communication that UNDERPIN adopts. It describes the stages involved and the adaptive measures put in place to ensure the strategy remains responsive to new opportunities and challenges. This section also highlights the importance of active partner collaboration in refining and executing the communication plan, ensuring that all activities are well-coordinated and target-specific audiences effectively.

2.4.1 Strategy overview

UNDERPIN aims for a long-term effect on the European and International level with specific activities for maximizing impact through dissemination, communication, and exploitation of results during and beyond the project duration.

In this respect, UNDERPIN has conceived a unifying strategy for communication, dissemination, exploitation, and business growth, trying to maximise the potential of cross-fertilisation between these activities, fostering the combined effects of general communication, dissemination of specific peers'-driven messages, exploitation of new knowledge and ultimately diversification and business expansion through advanced products and services (business growth).

This unified strategy has been inspired by the approach of Horizon Europe (HE) about projects' impact¹, which is reflected in the so-called Quadruple Helix model adding an additional, necessary dimension, namely that of the "natural environment", as shown in *Figure 1* to form the

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/other/event210609.htm>, June 2021: Novelities of Horizon Europe on Dissemination & Exploitation

Quintuple Helix Innovation model^{2,3}. This model will be further enhanced and used within the time frame of UNDERPIN, maximizing the project impact.

Figure 1 Quintuple Helix Innovation model

In short, the ultimate goal of the peer-based dissemination of results consists in providing a clearly understandable outreach to all main outcomes from various viewpoints, technical or business-related or relevant from a learning perspective. Communication activities are meant to raise the interest of different stakeholders and engage end-users for feedback on the implementation.

Last, leveraging on the network effect, the exploitation activities will be devoted to fostering the market potential of products and solutions, while considering different applications for the developed technologies and services. The exploitation plan will be finalised to get a proper understanding of the market, identify key products and solutions, define IPRs management, and conceive the most effective marketing strategy.

2.4.2 Detailed methodology

To effectively address the communication requirements of the project, a structured approach has been developed. This involves four critical stages:

²The Quintuple Helix innovation model: global warming as a challenge and driver for innovation, Elias G Carayannis, Thorsten D Barth & David FJ Campbell, Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship, Aug. 2012

³ Unveiling the Evolution of Innovation Ecosystems: An Analysis of Triple, Quadruple, and Quintuple Helix Model Innovation Systems in European Case Studies Rallou Taratori, Paulina Rodriguez-Fiscal, Marie Abigail Pacho, Sesil Koutra, Montserrat Pareja-Eastaway and Dimitrios Thomas, MDPI, July 2021

Figure 2 Communication strategy stages

Throughout the project, the communication and dissemination strategy and action plan will be periodically revised and enhanced by the collaboration of partners and stakeholders, adapting to newly identified opportunities.

Additional activities proposed or requested by project partners will be incorporated into the action plan and communicated through appropriate channels. The dissemination effort is focused on capturing the interest of SMEs, professionals in the field, the scientific community, and policymakers at both national and European levels. It is crucial to tailor the communication strategy to the intended audience, employing specific tactics and tools to engage the target group effectively.

Optimal outcomes in communicating and disseminating project activities are achieved when all partners actively participate in exchanging ideas and collaboratively promote the project's endeavours. The CD Board plays a crucial role in this regard. The scope of partners' activities encompasses but is not restricted to, disseminating project-related content through social media, their own newsletters, and websites, as well as engaging with pertinent media outlets (including print, radio, television, and online platforms) and stakeholders. A centralized document, CD Report Table, will serve as a repository for documenting these efforts. Furthermore, it is imperative that all partners actively communicate with the CDB regarding their project-related endeavours, including participation in conferences, alongside updates on the project's progress and outcomes.

As the project unfolds and communication and dissemination efforts proceed, it is vital for partners to continually reassess the core message to ensure it resonates with the specific audience. Moreover, the communication approach will evolve to become more targeted, enhancing the impact and reach of the project's key messages.

2.5 Reporting

Monitoring and evaluating dissemination activities will be conducted throughout the entire project cycle.

A reporting table for communication and dissemination activities will be established, with each partner regularly updating it by adding the essential data such as links, pictures, videos, etc., to validate the activity. Each partner will share this data with the chair of CDB on request or every two months, while the chair of CDB will report to the PM on the progress via status reports at regular intervals every three months and will prepare bi-annual progress reports with recommendations for GA meetings.

Partners will contribute to the dissemination and dissemination report by providing draft minutes from their events (conferences, workshops, seminars, or meetings). They will update the CDB chair before, during, or after the event to facilitate the communication of the activity through the project's digital channels. Partners attending any of the events will write an article about the event, focusing on how the UNDERPIN project was involved or presented.

These communication and dissemination reports will evaluate the outcomes of various dissemination activities. Evaluation will be done by reaching specified targets for a range of key indicators that are specified in section 2.7 *Measuring metrics* of this document.

2.6 EU communication guidelines

Recipients of EU funding are required to prominently feature the EU emblem in their communications as a way of recognizing the support granted through EU programs and enhancing the EU's visibility. There is a fundamental duty for all beneficiaries to promote awareness and visibility of the EU. A key aspect of fulfilling this obligation includes the accurate and conspicuous placement of the EU emblem, accompanied by a straightforward statement acknowledging the financial support from the EU.⁴

All UNDERPIN's CDP actions will ensure the visibility of the EU funding received by acknowledging the origin. UNDERPIN will use the EU's emblem correctly and prominently, as the single most important visual brand used to acknowledge the origin and ensure the visibility of EU funding, following the operational guidelines and EU emblem rules for recipients of EU funding.

The ready-to-use EU emblem including the funding statement is available to all the partners in SharePoint (Communication/Visuals/EU co-founded EN) but also can be downloaded in all EU languages from the original source of the European Commission's webpage:
https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/logos_downloadcenter

In all public communications, including visual materials related to the UNDERPIN project, the project partners are required to display the EU emblem alongside the funding statement. Variants of the emblem and guidelines for its use are accessible on SharePoint.

⁴ The use of the EU emblem in the context of EU Programmes 2021-2027, European Commission, March 2021

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The EU emblem must remain unaltered and cannot be combined with any other graphical elements or text. When displaying additional logos alongside the EU emblem, ensure that the emblem is at minimum the same size as the largest of these logos. No other visual identity or logo besides the EU emblem may be used to signify EU support.⁵

The partners are encouraged to use the co-funding statement wherever feasible:

This project has received funding from the Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101123179.

In scenarios where it is not possible to use the above statement or the EU emblem, such as in articles, posts, or similar formats, it is advisable to mention EU co-funding to ensure it is accounted for in communication and dissemination reports. Examples include:

- “a project co-founded through the Digital Europe Programme”,
- “co-funded by the European Union” etc.

Every document, webpage, or similar communication must explicitly state that the European Union's agencies or the EU Commission bear no responsibility for the content published. Responsibility rests solely with the authors or the project consortium, representing only their viewpoints. All communication and dissemination activities associated with the action must clarify that the content reflects only the author's perspective and that the EU agencies and the Commission cannot be held accountable for how the information is utilized.

The phrase that can be used:

Disclaimer: The webpage and documents reflect only the author's views, and the European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

2.7 Measuring metrics (KPIs)

The effectiveness of the Dissemination and Communication Plan will be evaluated by reaching specified targets for a range of key indicators. This chapter defines measuring metrics (KPIs) that relate to planned communication and dissemination activities.

A Key Performance Indicator (KPI) is a measurable value that demonstrates how effectively a project is achieving key objectives over time. These indicators serve as benchmarks for project partners, offering goals to aim for, milestones to monitor progress, and valuable insights to enhance decision-making. KPIs are crucial benchmarks that align with and advance the project's strategic goals, directing all partners towards pivotal areas of focus.

⁵ Ibid.

2.7.1 Dissemination KPIs

This section describes all the relevant KPIs, that will be utilised to measure the efficiency of the project dissemination activities. The evaluation will be conducted at the conclusion of each year of the project, commencing from Year 1. At the end of every reporting period, a thorough comparison between the annual target and the actual achieved value will be carried out, to ensure systematic improvement. All dissemination efforts will be systematically evaluated for effectiveness with the use of KPIs.

It must be pointed out that all principal investigators from research and academia involved in UNDERPIN comprise well-recognised experts in their field and they participate in wider associations in their fields of expertise, ensuring this way the successful dissemination of UNDERPIN results and research findings. Achievable qualitative and quantitative targets will be set during the dissemination planning. Our initial targets are described in the table below.

Table 2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for measuring dissemination-related activities

Channel	KPI	Method of measurement	Frequency	Threshold
Events – Up to 25 participants (UNDERPIN - organized events, international workshops, dissemination visits)	Number of events	Manually	End of project	>=4
	Number of audience contacts	Surveys	On schedule	At least 50% of the participants
	Number of participants Interested on UNDERPIN project	Surveys	On schedule	At least 40% of the participants
Events – 25-100 participants (professional events with relevant end-users and authorities, international Scientific workshops)	Number of events	Manually	End of project	>=2
	Number of audience contacts	Surveys	On schedule	At least 30% of the participants
	Number of participants interested on UNDERPIN project	Surveys	On schedule	At least 20% of the participants
Events – more than 100 participants (Conferences – UNDERPIN relevant)	Number of events	Manually	End of project	>=2
	Number of participants for UNDERPIN section contacted	Surveys	On schedule	At least 50% of the participants
	Number of participants for UNDERPIN section interested in the project	Surveys	On schedule	At least 40% of the participants
Journal publications	Number of journal publications by UNDERPIN partners	Direct reporting	End of project	>=4
Presentations in International Conferences	Number of conference presentations by UNDERPIN partners (persons involved)	Direct reporting	End of project	>=8

2.7.2 Communication KPIs

The aspect of monitoring how effective a strategy is is to monitor the impact of all communications where impact indicators and metrics will be monitored and analysed to improve the cost-effectiveness of the communication products and activities via a feedback loop. The different metrics may be monitored in different time cycles. Example metrics include standard website metrics, user behaviour metrics, promotional metrics such as backlinks, SEO ranking, etc., quantitative data measured via a survey (suggested – under consideration), as well as outreach that covers indicators concerning press coverage, social media, etc.

In this respect, a set of KPIs with respect to communication, will be monitored and managed by the WP lead. This will allow corrective measures to be taken and enforced, whenever the performance and progress marked by the consortium are not aligned with the set objectives. In this respect, the following table shows the KPIs related to communication activities as defined by the project at proposal preparation time.

Table 3 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for measuring communication-related activities

Channel	KPI	Method of measurement	Frequency	Threshold
UNDERPIN website	Number of the website visitors per year	Google Analytics	Yearly	>= 500
UNDERPIN portal	Number of the portal visitors per year	Google Analytics	Yearly	>= 500
Social Networks LinkedIn (public)	Number of followers	LinkedIn	Total	>=600
	View of UNDERPIN profile	LinkedIn	Total	>=5000
Social Networks YouTube	Number of subscribers	YouTube	Total	>=50
	Number of video views	YouTube	Total	>=500

Monthly analyses of the website are conducted using Google Analytics to assess the number of visitors, their origins, and the duration of their visits. This data will be included in the activity reports.

For the UNDERPIN social media channels, metrics such as the number of followers on the LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook UNDERPIN page, subscribers to the UNDERPIN YouTube channel, and subscribers to the UNDERPIN Newsletter will be monitored regularly and reported in the activity reports as well.

3 Tools and channels

The following list illustrates the dissemination activities, which will be conducted with the use of the tool and channels during and after the project.

3.1 Project identity

To easily follow the branding concept, all materials and templates will be shared with partners. This includes visual identity and logo, leaflets and flyers, roll-up design, memos, meeting minutes and attendance list templates, a PowerPoint presentation template, etc. While most materials and templates will be pre-prepared, the development of new materials will be considered in response to identified needs or in accordance with partners' suggestions.

3.1.1 Logo

The book of standards contains the rules of the communication system. These rules are to be followed strictly to maintain brand consistency. The document includes logos, typeface, colors, and font. The book of standards will be available on the internal communication platform for partners to use.

A designed logo is available and should be utilized in all publications and communications for instant recognition. This practice will enhance consistency in the information generated across partner organizations.

The logo consists of a symbol and a typeface. Two options are available: horizontal and vertical orientation.

UNDERPIN

UNDERPIN

The logo mark symbolizes a seamless exchange of information among European manufacturers, reflecting advancements in manufacturing technologies driven by data-driven knowledge and collaborative innovation.

The use of logo and logo mark is explained in detail in the book of standards as well as all its variations for darker and lighter backgrounds.

Fonts that will be used to represent the project are:

- For communication and templates – Aptos
- For printed and digital materials – Inter (primary font)

All iterations of the logo, logo mark, and accompanying fonts will be available through a shared platform for partners to use.

The color palette embodies our project essence: black for reliability, crayola for sustainability, bright turquoise for innovation, and capri for trust. These colors represent technology, sustainability, innovation, and collaboration within manufacturing.

3.1.2 Document templates

The visual identity of the project also encompasses various document templates, which will be accessible to all partners as the official templates of the project. Some of these templates have already been created, while others will be made available upon request.

Available templates:

- memo template
- meeting minutes
- attendance list (short and long)
- agenda
- PowerPoint presentation
- report templates
- deliverables templates

The **presentation templates and deliverable template** ensure visual coherence between the presentations and dissemination activities from each project partner. To this, they feature a consistent design and will be employed for both internal and external events, ensuring the continuity of corporate branding and visibility on all occasions. All of the aforementioned digital assets are available for each partner of the consortium in the project SharePoint.

3.2 Project website

The UNDERPIN website is designed to be the premier touchpoint for initial information, offering a comprehensive overview of the project to all visitors. It showcases the project goals, results, and the consortium behind it. The website is a work in progress and will be continuously updated with the new information.

The official web domain is: www.underpinproject.eu

Acting as the primary platform for disseminating information and results, the website provides timely updates on the project’s progress, including activities, achievements, publications, announcements for meetings and events such as workshops and conferences, etc. It also houses a variety of resources for interested stakeholders, such as downloadable project brochures, a newsletter subscription form, and other materials for widespread distribution.

The website was officially launched in month three (M3).

The general communication goal is to continuously increase the traffic on the website and convert potential visitors into users of the platform. With good communication and clear target group communication we will convince the visitor to join UNDERPIN or to support it.

Keywords defined at the beginning of the project: “underpin project”, “underpin data space”, “data space for manufacturing”, “manufacturing industry”, “predictive/ prescriptive maintenance”, “dynamic asset management”, “refinery”, “wind farms”, “renewable energy sector”.

Figure 3 UNDERPIN website - Home page

3.2.1 Structure

The UNDERPIN website in the first phase consists of the following pages:

- **Home page** – A brief introduction to the project.
- **About the project** – Detailed explanation of the project.
- **Consortium** – A list of partners, each with a short description.
- **Work Packages** – An overview of project activities organized into work packages. Objectives and deliverables are specified for each WP.
- **Use Cases** – The development and testing of the UNDERPIN Data Space are based on two dynamic pilots. To better understand how the data space will be developed, these UCs are explained here.
- **News** – Articles and announcements that keep visitors informed about project progress and act as a dissemination channel.
- **Contact** – basic contact form for visitors and potential stakeholders to contact us.

3.2.2 Website data and statistics

Having in mind the General Data Protection Regulation, our website has a Privacy Policy as well as the Terms and Conditions of Web Use clearly stated. When visiting the website, we collect certain data for statistical purposes. This data will be evaluated anonymously, e.g. to improve the use of the website.

Analytical cookies are used to understand how visitors interact with the website. These cookies help provide information on metrics such as the number of visitors, bounce rate, traffic source, etc. Google Analytics sets this type of cookies to calculate visitor, session, and campaign data and track site usage for the site's analytics report, as well as to store and count page views. The cookie stores information anonymously and assigns a randomly generated number to recognise unique visitors.

Necessary cookies are required to enable the basic features of this site, such as providing secure log-in or adjusting your consent preferences. These cookies do not store any personally identifiable data.

We only collect personally identifiable data (such as email addresses) when a visitor has voluntarily submitted it. Visitors of our website may volunteer personal information in the following circumstances: to subscribe to newsletters or make general inquiries. We do not collect personal information unless it has been submitted to us.

3.2.3 Interactive website tools

The UNDERPIN project is poised to enhance the digital skills landscape by launching a suite of interactive web tools designed to engage and educate a diverse audience. From M2 to M24, on the project website, a dedicated space (“platform”) will serve as a hub for knowledge dissemination and interactive learning, targeting an array of stakeholders that includes interested visitors and a wider DS community, business professionals keen to learn about value creation

through data, industrial/business decision-makers, researchers, students for the purpose of their research and training activities.

The platform will offer modular educational content tailored to impart practical knowledge on data use and provision, catering to those interested in unlocking value creation through data. Recognizing the varied learning preferences and the need for engaging content, the platform will not only feature leaflets, booklets, presentations, documents, and traditional blogs but also introduce video vlogs. These vlogs aim to deliver short, impactful, and easily digestible messages, and enable a direct exchange with website visitors/interested stakeholders.

There is a special focus on empowering SMEs, recognizing their critical role in the industry and their potential to benefit significantly from data-driven innovations. By providing resources that are both informative and accessible, UNDERPIN reaffirms its commitment to fostering an inclusive data space community where knowledge sharing leads to collective advancement.

3.3 Social media channels

The presence of the UNDERPIN project will be showcased across the established social media channels. Social media platforms will be utilized to effectively convey information about the project, and its events, disseminate results, outputs, and milestones, as well as issue call-to-actions to a wider audience.

The project will be available on the following social media:

Network	Link	Tag
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/underpin-project	@underpinproject
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/underpindataspace	@underpindataspace
Twitter	https://twitter.com/UnderpinProject	@underpinproject
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@underpinproject	@underpinproject

Social media channels will enhance and supplement communication on the project website, focusing on specific groups aligned with the overall structure of social media users.

To broaden the impact of the social media outreach, the chair of the CDB will actively support project partners in disseminating information through their existing social media channels. This support will involve:

- Reminders: WP6 lead will send periodic email reminders or include updates in internal newsletters, prompting project partners to reshare content from the project’s social media accounts and share information within their networks.
- Content: The WP6 lead will create content and visuals for CDB Members (project partners) to utilize on their digital channels. This includes providing timetables specifying when, where, and what to publish. Each partner will tailor their communication to align with their organization’s requirements.

On the other hand, the CDB Members will actively contribute to disseminating project results:

- regularly check social media and reshare/repost/retweet/republish the latest posts
- publish their own unique content following the rules of the project communication.

This collaborative approach aims to maximize the project visibility and engagement across diverse networks.

Additional notes and recommendations for social media communication:

- Main project hashtags: #UnderpinProject #UnderpinDataSpace
- Other hashtags (not limited): #EUproject #Manufacturing #ManufacturingExcellence #ManufacturingSolutions
- When referring to the UNDERPIN project, the social media manager will ensure that 'UNDERPIN project' is tagged to the project social media page using '@'
- posts published on the project`s channel will tag each partner`s social media page

3.3.1 LinkedIn

Given the project`s B2B orientation and specific target audience, special emphasis will be placed on LinkedIn as a communication and dissemination (CD) channel. As the world's largest professional network online (1 billion users globally⁶), LinkedIn will facilitate the establishment and strengthening of professional relationships with the intended audience.

To offer an immediate and responsive channel for communication LinkedIn tools will be used, such as discussion, newsletter, educational posts (slides), etc.

3.3.2 YouTube

YouTube is an online video-sharing and social media platform that will be used for the publication of project videos. The project videos will be embedded on the website and shared via other project social media channels. YouTube also offers private channels/ videos that will be shared with specific audiences.

3.4 Promotion materials & leaflets

The promotional leaflets will be produced for the UNDERPIN project, aimed at effectively communicating its objectives, methodologies, partner involvement, and benefits to the target audience. The leaflets will be produced primarily in English. On request and with the help of the project partners they can be translated in local language as well.

The content and design of the leaflet are being carefully planned to ensure clarity and effectiveness in conveying the project`s message. This includes discussions with all partners to refine the structure, content, and design according to the project's evolving strategy and specific tasks` objectives. Among other aims, the leaflet can and will offer valuable insights into the

⁶ Source: <https://www.demandsage.com/linkedin-statistics/>; 22 March 2024

project's activities and overarching goals, serving as a key tool for dissemination and outreach efforts.

Leaflets will be distributed at various events and shared online for easy access. Additionally, to maintain a consistent brand presence at events such as trade fairs and conferences, roll-ups will be designed and produced. Other materials can and will be produced in case of necessity (posters, brochures, etc.)

Promotional materials will play an important role in raising awareness about the UNDERPIN project and engaging with its target audience effectively, especially during the UNDERPIN road show.

For educational purposes of specific target groups and a better understanding of data spaces and the UNDERPIN project, digital flyers, visuals, infographics, etc. will be prepared and shared via digital channels. A dedicated sub-page at www.underpinproject.eu will be created for all downloadable materials and public documents of the UNDERPIN project.

All promotional materials' print preparation will be available in SharePoint for partners to print them by themselves on demand.

Figure 4 Flyer 1 – two-pager flyer (A5 format) – page 1 and 2

Figure 5 Roll-up (200x85cm)

3.5 Press releases

Throughout the project duration, a minimum of six press releases will be issued following the achievement of key milestones or in response to noteworthy developments. Press releases aim to record all the activities of the project and inform the general public and the key target audience about the project.

The initial press release regarding the Kick-off meeting in Athens (19 December 2023) has already been distributed across various channels belonging to the project consortium's press distribution networks.

Link to the first press release published at the UNDERPIN website:

<https://underpinproject.eu/news/marking-the-launch-of-the-underpin-project/>

At this stage, specific topics have not been fixed, allowing flexibility in topic selection. Each project partner is tasked with broadcasting every press release through their respective organizational channels to broaden their reach. This includes posting on their websites, disseminating through local, regional, and national press lists (covering radio, television, and print media), as well as leveraging social media platforms and their newsletters.

Each partner is responsible for Press Releases' adaptation to the local context, translation into their mother tongues, as well as its dissemination to the local media.

3.6 Newsletter

UNDERPIN is set to launch a newsletter targeting stakeholders. This initiative will involve collecting relevant email addresses from all consortium partners, through a subscription option on the project website and via LinkedIn, all in compliance with GDPR.

The newsletter aims to offer concise updates on the project's latest developments, achievements, announcements, and interviews, supplementing other dissemination efforts. By the project conclusion, it aims to engage over 600 individuals.

Each newsletter will be documented in the activity report. Partners are encouraged to propose potential topics to the Chair of the CDB, who will then develop the content, incorporating text, images, and design. The content will reflect the progress of each work package, with updates provided by the lead beneficiary of the work package.

3.7 Articles (scientific and non-scientific)

To increase the outreach of the project to the scientific community, the UNDERPIN consortium aims to publish at least five (>5) scientific publications to sector-specific (computer science, food safety, etc.) leading international journals or conferences that will be edited by project partners and other contributors pertaining the project and the outcomes of the different use cases. Some examples include:

- IEEE International Conference on Service-Oriented System Engineering
- International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, Computing and Data Communication Systems (icABCD)
- Elsevier Journal of Systems and Software
- Journal of Industrial Information Integration

Moreover, the following publications are also expected:

- A publication of the Market Analysis
- White paper of the results coming from experimental evaluations

3.8 Events

A key channel that will streamline the dissemination activities of the project is one of the interactive events. In general, the consortium endeavors to arrange dedicated sessions or workshops for each pilot project within prominent conferences, aiming to enhance visibility and engagement, exchange of knowledge and experiences, and networking with relevant stakeholders in the field. Apart from organizing events and special sessions or workshops in conferences and trade fairs, the consortium partners will participate in policy events,

conferences, hackathons, workshops, and forums to disseminate the objectives and the outcomes of the project.

Through the project period, UNDERPIN partners will organise meetings and events as follows:

- **Kick-off event:** The project started with the **Kick-off event (M1)** held on 19 December 2023 in Athens, Greece, organised by the project coordinator MOH. All project partners participated. It was a hybrid event, also available to all project partners and external partners via direct video link.
- **Plenary Consortium Meetings:** Throughout the project period, **4 consortium meetings** will be organised every 6 months. The meetings will be held in Cyprus (M6), Austria (M12), Slovenia (M18), and Greece (M24). The Final Conference will be held together with the last consortium meeting in Greece.
- **Final Project Event:** UNDERPIN will conclude with the Final and Press conference (**M24**) in Greece, reporting to the target audiences as identified throughout the project delivery on results achieved, pathway creation for federated data spaces, UNDERPIN's next steps (sustainability), future perspectives and potential for data creation/use beyond the project end (conclusion of UNDERPIN, presentation of results, impacts, perspectives for continuation; interactive presentation for clear demonstration of data value creation). Additional promo materials will be prepared for all attendees.
- **Datathons and Tech Workshops:** Over the project period 6 one-week datathons and 4 technical workshops (WS) will be organised in Austria, Greece, Cyprus, and Bulgaria. Attendance is expected from WP2, WP3, WP4 leaders and contributors.
- **Standardisation WS:** 2 standardisation workshops will be co-organised / supported: (i) for Semantic Interoperability in Data Spaces together with W3C (World Wide Web Consortium), BDVA (Big Data Value Association, and IDSA (International Data Space Association) back to back with European Big Data Value Forum 2024 in October in Budapest, Hungary, and (ii) for CEN-WSA (European Committee for Standardisation) / CENELEC (European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation) will be organised in Greece. Kick-off will be held in M6 and Final Review WS in M24.
- **UNDERPIN Data Space Roadshow** across Europe to promote and demonstrate the UNDERPIN Data Space to the target groups. (*Detail description under the section 5.5.*)
- **Organisation of hybrid DS events, webinars, conferences, industry gatherings, workshops, and meetings (M1-M24),** liaison with the portfolio activities, other DS initiatives, and other relevant EU-funded projects to share lessons learned and good practices with other stakeholders, such as Data Spaces Support Centre, governance body identified by the preparatory action EU DATA SP4CE, Digital Innovation Hubs for a broad uptake by the industry, Testing and Experimentation Facility for Manufacturing, the Manufacturing Data Space for Supply Chain Management, combining online and offline events for the widest possible reach.

For every event, an agenda will be prepared and shared with all participants. Every organisation of events will follow the provisions of the GREEN CHARTER on the sustainable implementation of project activities and event organisation. During the execution of the project and in the

coordination of meetings and events, UNDERPIN is committed to advocating for sustainable practices across all activities. This includes urging partners to opt for transportation options that are lower in carbon emissions and more environmentally friendly when traveling to project-related functions. Examples of this are choosing train travel over flying for longer distances, or public transport over personal vehicles for daily commutes. To facilitate the adoption of these greener travel methods, which may require more time, all activities will be scheduled and communicated well in advance. Moreover, to minimize unnecessary travel, we will utilize a blend of in-person and virtual meeting formats, employing teleconferencing tools where physical presence is not essential. We will also promote the minimal or zero use of printed materials in our activities.

3.9 Ambassador programme

Task T6.3 – *Large-scale dissemination of project impacts and results* will be carried out through the creation of an Ambassador Programme. The programme will involve early adopters, committed industry players, supporting initiatives, etc. in the development and fine-tuning of case studies and services, aiming at making this first group of users the first promoters of project results.

By involving these participants in the development process, they naturally become knowledgeable and passionate advocates for the project. As ambassadors, they are ideally positioned to champion the project impacts and results within their networks and communities, helping to catalyze wider adoption and recognition. The programme serves not only as a dissemination tool but also creates a feedback loop for continuous improvement and market relevance of the project outputs.

Early adopters in an Ambassador Programme can be instrumental in both refining the project deliverables and promoting its results. Some of the activities that will be suggested and tested with the UNDERPIN Ambassadors:

- Provide them with all necessary materials and knowledge to effectively use and advocate for the project.
- Use their insights to fine-tune the project outcomes and to create the new communication materials.
- Encourage them to create and share content such as blogs, case studies, testimonials, and social media posts about their experiences with the UNDERPIN project and UNDERPIN Data Space.
- Involve early adopters in community discussions, webinars, live Q&A sessions, and workshops related to the project, where they can share their success stories.
- Enable them to attend or speak at industry events, acting as project representatives.
- Feature their endorsements in promotional materials, on social media, and on the project website.

By engaging early adopters through these activities, we empower them to be advocates for the project and to facilitate the improvement and expansion of the project through their valuable input and reach.

4 Community building

This chapter includes additional dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities with a focus on cooperation, clustering, capacity building, and stakeholder engagement. These activities will be crucial to ensure the outreach and to involve a continuously growing number of participants from the manufacturing domain and beyond, with a clear and strong focus on European SMEs.

4.1 Sustainability and Ecosystem Board

To ensure the efficient delivery of community building, outreach, and stakeholder engagement actions, and orchestrating DS ecosystem actions, the Sustainability and Ecosystem Board (SEB) has been established. The primary goal of SEB is to consistently populate the UNDERPIN Data Space.

Each beneficiary has designated a representative to serve on the Sustainability and Ecosystem Board (SEB), which will be chaired by the consortium coordinator MOH's representative. MOH as the lead beneficiary of WP 5, will appoint the Community Manager to oversee the effective execution of defined actions.

The SEB will maintain close ties with the EAB and CDB to orchestrate consortium-level actions of the data space ecosystem creation.

4.2 External Advisory Board

The formation of the EXTERNAL ADVISORY BOARD (EAB) comprises experts from leading institutions and organizations in the field, including the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), strategic partners of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) in Slovenia, specialists in dataspace business models, professionals in PR and the media industry, among others. Tasked with scrutinizing the project program, the EAB will provide advice and propose strategies, aligning with EU-wide data space initiatives.

Additionally, the EAB will assist the UNDERPIN consortium in creating an ecosystem by leveraging partner networks across target stakeholder landscapes to populate the UNDERPIN data space according to defined KPIs. Furthermore, the EAB will offer guidance to UNDERPIN on matters related to business models and sustainability. While the EAB will formally convene annually alongside GA meetings, additional digital meeting options may be utilized if necessary.

The genuine purpose of the EAB will become evident through the T5.4 Commercialization initiatives and action plan, which will explore and outline UNDERPIN's go-to-market strategy. A comprehensive analysis and strategy will be delineated in Deliverable *D5.3 Business Engagement and Commercialization Plan*.

4.3 International Data Spaces Association (IDSA)

International Data Spaces Association IDSA is the founding member of the Data Space Support Center (DSSC), which is driving Data Space adoption through support activities, a platform and web portal for knowledge and asset sharing, a help desk, toolboxes, and active engagement with the CoP. IDSA will bring expertise and knowledge about this and future developments to IDSA.

IDSA will help in the following tasks and scope of objectives:

- **T5.2: Sustainable Business Models** to support business model development bringing its expertise in the field from other Data Spaces.
- **T5.4: Commercialisation initiatives and Action Plan** to support the action plan development.
- **T6.4: Orchestration, Standardisation, and Certification** to establish a strong relationship with the Data Spaces Support Centre.
- **T6.5: Community Building and Scale-Out** to support community building, adoption and scale out of the UNDERPIN Data Space across Europe.

The International Data Spaces Association, IDSA will support UNDERPIN with the following activities:

- to build and establish the UNDERPIN community,
- to participate in the External Advisory Board (EAB), and act as the liaison with the CSA manufacturing as well as with IDS and GAIA-X working groups. Furthermore,
- act as liaison to UNDERPIN by passing on and communicating on Data Spaces Blueprint (composed of common building blocks encompassing the business, legal, operational, technical, and societal aspects of data spaces) that continuously evolves (with a user-centric approach) as the result of co-creation with the stakeholders, that form the Community of Practice (CoP) in the field of data sharing and they create and adopt the Blueprint and its building blocks in sectoral data spaces.

IDSA will support UNDERPIN orchestration with relevant initiatives, to promote and scale and adopt the UNDERPIN Data Space to become a European Manufacturing Data Space.

4.4 Multiplier (stakeholder) engagement

Multiplier and stakeholder engagement is crucial for the success of UNDERPIN. To do so, as has already been mentioned, we will follow the approach below:

- **Identify Stakeholders:** This includes companies up and down the supply chain, research institutions, government agencies, and potential data consumers.
- **Segment Stakeholders:** Group stakeholders based on their interests and needs.

- **Develop Engagement Strategies:** Tailor communication and engagement approaches for each group. This could involve workshops, webinars, online forums, or individual meetings.
- **Highlight Benefits:** Clearly communicate the benefits of participating in the data space, such as improved efficiency, cost reduction, or access to valuable data insights.
- **Address Concerns:** Proactively address concerns about data privacy, security, and governance.

Here are some additional tips:

- **Establish an Advisory Board:** A board with representatives from key stakeholder groups can provide valuable guidance and feedback.
- **Implement our Communication Plan:** This plan should outline how you will communicate with stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle.

Some relevant initiatives that we will target are:

- **International Data Spaces (IDS):** An initiative focused on creating a global network of interoperable data spaces. Focuses on technical aspects and establishing common standards <https://internationaldataspaces.org/>.
- **European Commission's Common European Data Spaces:** Aims to create a single market for data in the EU, with specific data spaces for various sectors like health, manufacturing, and energy <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces>.
- **GAIA-X:** A German initiative for a secure, open, and federated data infrastructure for Europe. While not strictly a data space initiative, it has some overlap and shares similar goals <https://gaia-x.eu/what-is-gaia-x/>.

Connecting with these initiatives allows UNDERPIN to share best practices and learn from others, increase the visibility of the UNDERPIN solutions, attract new participants and data providers, as well as contribute to the development of a standardized data space ecosystem in Europe.

4.5 UNDERPIN Data Space Roadshow across Europe

A vital role in scaling out the UNDERPIN Data Space according to the plans outlined in WP5 for success is task T6.5 "Community Building and Scale-Out".

To successfully scale out the project, in Y2 of the project, a roadshow will be organised. Starting in M12, the UNDERPIN Data Space Roadshow will promote and showcase the UNDERPIN Data Space to target groups, particularly SMEs in manufacturing. The roadshow, spanning around 10 locations across Europe, will coincide with existing events, including industry and UNDERPIN's own gatherings (e.g., GA meetings). This strategic alignment aims to streamline event organization, maximize impact, and tightly integrate with other tasks in WP6. Each roadshow stop, designed as a half-day workshop, will have a clear agenda and incentive model for participants. UNDERPIN plans to collaborate with European Digital Innovation Hubs, DSSC, and

other Data Space CSAs and projects to enhance outreach and act as multipliers for UNDERPIN's initiatives.

The UNDERPIN Data Space Roadshow represents a significant effort to scale up the project and attract new users. Partner collaboration is essential for the success of the roadshow. By leveraging existing events, collaborating with key stakeholders, and offering clear incentives, the roadshow has the potential to significantly expand the reach of the UNDERPIN Data Space.

Some key points already identified for covering the roadshow, are:

- **Goal:** Promote and showcase the UNDERPIN Data Space to target groups, particularly SMEs in manufacturing.
- **Timeline:**
 - Start: M12 (Year 2 of the project)
 - Duration: the Roadshow will span across 10 locations across Europe.
- **Event Alignment:** Each stop will strategically coincide with existing industry events or UNDERPIN gatherings (e.g., GA meetings) to maximize impact and streamline the organization.
- **Format:** Each location will host a half-day workshop with a clear agenda and an incentive model designed to attract participants.
- **Collaboration:** UNDERPIN plans to collaborate with key stakeholders to enhance outreach:
 - European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs)
 - Data Space Support Centre (DSSC)
 - International Data Space Association (IDSA) and its national hubs
 - Other Data Space CSA (Collaborative Service Agreements) projects
- **Next Steps and Partner Communication:**
 - Location Selection: The specific locations for the 10 roadshow stops are still under development. The selection process will likely involve considering factors like:
 - Presence of a large concentration of target audience (SMEs in manufacturing)
 - Existing industry events or UNDERPIN gatherings that can be leveraged for co-location
 - Geographical spread to ensure pan-European reach
 - Event Selection: Specific industry events or UNDERPIN gatherings to be aligned with are also being identified. Partners will be informed once the final list of locations and events is confirmed.
 - Communication Plan: A detailed communication plan outlining the roadshow schedule, locations, and participation details will be produced and distributed to partners well in advance. This will allow partners to promote the roadshow within their networks and encourage potential participants from their regions.

4.6 Participation in external events

Each consortium member actively participates in their respective national Digital Innovation Hubs, and partnerships will be established for countries without representation. UNDERPIN aims to collaborate with relevant national and international organizations, such as industry associations, business agencies, and the European Factories of the Future Research Association (EFFRA), to act as multipliers. These collaborative efforts are crucial for successfully scaling out the UNDERPIN Data Space into an established European Data Space for Manufacturing.

Given the prevalence of virtual information, partners will engage in project events, information days, expert meetings, and workshops with diverse target groups to establish sustainable face-to-face contacts. Participation in events, conferences, workshops, and meetings (M1–M24) is an inherent dissemination activity for UNDERPIN, with a focus on attending DSSC events, CSA preparatory actions, other Manufacturing Data Space initiatives, EBDVF (European Big Data Value Forum), and the annual IDSA (International Data Spaces Association) summit. This participation serves to share lessons learned and best practices with other stakeholders.

To ensure transparency regarding upcoming events partners intend to attend, an Events Table has been created and circulated among partners. This table is designed to facilitate coordination, enable shared participation in events, and collectively enhance the promotion of the UNDERPIN project.

To date, partners have identified eight events they aim to attend (or have already attended) in 2024. Given that the UNDERPIN Data Space roadshow is scheduled for the second year of the project, this list is expected to expand based on the outcomes of collaboration.

DATE	NAME OF THE EVENT	VENUE	TYPE
14.2.2024	Tiko Pro Podjetniški zajtrk 2024 Kje bodo nepovratna sredstva?	Maribor, Slovenia	Workshop (online)
15.2.2024	TIKO PRO PODUZETNIČKI DORUČAK 2024. Gdje se skrivaju bespovratna sredstva?	Zagreb, Croatia	Workshop (online)
12-14.3.2024	Data Spaces Symposium	Darmstadt, Germany	Conference
6-10.5.2024	Knowledge Graph Conference 2024 (KGC24)	New York City, USA	Conference
26-30.5.2024	ESWC 2024	Heraklion, Greece	Conference, Workshop
3-5.7.2024	8th european conference of the prognostics and health management	Prague, CZ	Conference
17-19.9.2024	SEMANTiCS 2024 Conference	Amsterdam, Netherlands	Conference
1.10.2024	Workshop on Semantic Interoperability in Data Spaces	Budapest, Hungary	Workshop
2-4.10.2024	European Big Data Value Forum 2024	Budapest, Hungary	Conference

As stated in section 2.5 *Reporting* of this document, partners will support dissemination efforts and reports by submitting an article detailing the event, with a particular focus on the UNDERPIN project involvement or presentation.

5 Document sharing

All essential communication and dissemination materials for partners are stored in SharePoint set up by project partner MOH. The dedicated folder 3. *Communication* currently houses:

1. Logo

- **Brand Guidelines** outlining the correct usage of the logo and project communication
- **Logotype** with all versions of logo for print (CMYK) and digital (RGB) use
- **Pattern** as a part of the visual identity

2. Visuals

- **EU co-founded EN** – The ready-to-use EU emblem including the funding statement. How to properly use the EU emblem is described in detail in section 3.6 *EU communication guidelines* of this document;
- **Flyers** – ready to print flyers;
- **Graphics – SM, web** – graphics available for partners to use in digital channels when communicating about UNDERPIN;
- **Photos – partner** – photos provided by partners for use in UNDERPIN communications;
- **Roll-up** – ready-to-print roll-up designs.

3. Templates – Document templates for official project documents, such as meeting minutes, agendas, attendance lists, deliverables, PowerPoint presentations, etc.

4. Partners Logo and Info – the logos and the company description of all project partners, which can be accessed and utilized for presentations and similar purposes as needed (in connection with UNDERPIN). Should there be any updates to a partner’s logo or company info during the project duration, these will be promptly updated. Partners are requested to notify the CDB chair of any changes. This information is used to present each partner on the project website.

All documentation in connection with the WP6 can be found in the dedicated folder 2. *WP/WP6*. It currently houses:

- 1. Press Releases** – PRs saved by date with accompanying visuals;
- 2. Events** – An event planner document for partners to contribute planned activities or suggestions; photos and documents from the attended event;
- 3. Reporting – dissemination** – all documents (texts, articles, visuals, print screens...) that can and will be used for dissemination reports (quarterly report, final deliverable, etc), including the *Report Table* template that each partner has to continuously update for its organisation. Each document has to include the date and place of publication as well as the partner’s name;
- 4. Website** – Documents directly related to the website, including texts, photos, and graphics;
- 5. Media planning** – A detailed *CD Media Plan* table and documents related to media plan implementation;
- 6. D6.1 CD Plan (initial design)** – the working document and all versions of the deliverable.

6 Conclusion

The CDP establishes a solid foundation for the dissemination of the UNDERPIN project. The dynamic document will serve as a guide for all partners, ensuring that communication activities are cohesive and strategically targeted. The success of the CDP will be gauged against specific KPIs, ensuring that the project's innovative solutions in data sharing and asset management are effectively communicated to the relevant stakeholders and the broader manufacturing community. As the project progresses, the document will be regularly reviewed and updated, with all changes reported in the periodic reports, keeping the dissemination strategy aligned with the project's growing scope and achievements.

References

1. E. G. Carayannis, Th. D. Barth & D. FJ Campbell: *The Quintuple Helix innovation model: global warming as a challenge and driver for innovation*; Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship, Aug 2012
2. European Commission: *Novelties of Horizon Europe on Dissemination & Exploitation*, June 2021 Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/other/event210609.htm>
3. European Commission: *The use of the EU emblem in the context of EU Programmes 2021-2027*, March 2021; Source: https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2021-05/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf
4. R. Taratori, P. Rodriguez-Fiscal, M. A. Pacho, S. Koutra, M. Pareja-Eastaway, D. Thomas: *Unveiling the Evolution of Innovation Ecosystems: An Analysis of Triple, Quadruple, and Quintuple Helix Model Innovation Systems in European Case Studies*; MDPI, July 2021

